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Abstract— This paper investigates the tile quality selection problem in multi-quality tiled 360° video streaming. We consider 360° video quality assessment (VQA) metrics, with the objective of maximizing the quality of the user’s viewport in bandwidth-constrained communication. We formulate the problem as a multiple-choice knapsack problem (MCKP) and apply a greedy algorithm to solve it. The simulation results validate the advantages of our proposed method, demonstrated as an improvement in the viewport’s weighted-to-spherical peak signal-to-noise ratio (WS-PSNR).

Keywords—video streaming, 360° videos, virtual reality (VR)

I. INTRODUCTION

360° videos and virtual reality (VR) applications have gained notable popularity among the evolving multimedia technologies. However, ensuring satisfactory quality of experience (QoE) levels when delivering 360° videos over communication networks is a challenging task. 360° videos have high data rates and are subject to tight latency constraints [1]. A VR user uses a head-mounted display (HMD) to explore the spherical scene by moving his/her head toward the desired direction. The viewed portion of the video is commonly referred to as the user’s viewport or field of view (FoV). Intuitively, transmitting only the viewport data to the user instead of sending the whole video should result in reducing the required bitrate.

In the context of 360° streaming, the spherical video is typically mapped into an equirectangular projection (ERP) shape which is then divided into smaller rectangular parts referred to as tiles. Each tile can be encoded and transmitted independently. In bandwidth-constrained scenarios, an efficient transmission involves choosing the tiles to be delivered and the quality level of each transmitted tile. Many works have been proposed to optimize the delivery of tiled 360° videos in different settings [2]-[4]. However, most of the available methods do not consider 360° video quality assessment (VQA) metrics in their optimization and focus on other criteria.

360° VQA metrics are specifically designed to provide an estimate of users’ satisfaction of a 360° video quality. In our work, we chose to target the viewport’s weighted-to-spherical peak signal-to-noise ratio (WS-PSNR). WS-PSNR is simple to calculate and reflects the actual perceived quality by the users. On another note, a tile location with respect to the user’s viewport decides its influence on the perceived quality. Therefore, we consider the tiles’ viewing percentages, in addition to their bitrates and quality levels, to maximize the viewport’s WS-PSNR in limited bandwidth scenarios. We formulate the problem as a multiple-choice knapsack problem (MCKP) and deploy a greedy algorithm for solving it.

II. RELATED WORK

Omnidirectional videos are usually transformed into two-dimensional shapes to benefit from compression tools that have been optimized for the encoding of conventional 2D videos [5]. In ERP, pixels on the sphere are mapped to form a 2D rectangular shape. In the context of 360° video streaming, the resulting ERP video is oftentimes divided into smaller rectangular tiles. These tiles are then encoded and transmitted independently. Since users watch only a subset of the overall tiles at any given time, tile-based streaming allows for higher flexibility and results in a considerable bitrate reduction [6].

Although video compression is integral for reducing video sizes to manageable levels, it also causes distortions in the videos that degrade the video quality as perceived by the user. Full-reference VQA methods have been developed to provide objective numerical metrics of distorted videos by comparing them to the original undistorted ones. The peak signal-to-noise ratio (PSNR) is a simple VQA method that entails the calculation of pixel value differences between the original and distorted videos on a frame-to-frame basis. Recently, the concept of VQA has been extended for 360° video assessment. The WS-PSNR [7] was developed as a 360° VQA method. WS-PSNR assigns weights to pixels according to their positions. Thus, capturing the actual influence of each pixel as observed in the spherical domain.

Many efforts have been directed toward the optimization of 360° video streaming through the selection of transmitted tiles and their qualities. The authors in [2], leveraged the arising multicast opportunities and optimized the available resources to minimize energy consumption. In [3], a learning-based solution has been proposed to address tile-based viewport adaptive streaming. They evaluate the performance of their method using a QoE metric that incorporates the average viewport tile bitrates, rebuffering time, smoothness, and viewport spatial quality variance. The authors in [4] considered tile portions and assessed their approach according to the delivered viewport PSNR. Despite existing work in this field, 360° VQA metrics have hardly been considered in the optimization of 360° streaming. This paper aims to address this gap and presents the problem formulation for tile quality selection as well as the evaluation of a greedy algorithm that maximizes the WS-PSNR within the user's FoV.

III. MOTIVATION & PROBLEM FORMULATION

Tile-based streaming introduces several advantages for 360° video transmission. However, it still leads to the transmission of unviewed content. Part of the transmitted tiles end up only partially watched. Depending on the location of these tiles within the user's FoV, only a small portion of them is displayed to the user. To illustrate these cases from a realistic scenario, Figure 1 shows the viewport location within the entire 360° video at a certain timestamp. It can be observed that only small portions of edge tiles lie within the viewport borders.

Since tiles are sent as temporal segments, it is also important to consider the watching percentage for each tile within the entire segment length. Although users can move their heads during the segment period, their FoVs tend not to change much within short time periods. Figure 2 presents an example of the resulting tile-watching percentages of a VR user, averaged over a one-second segment. Within the video segment, tiles located at the center of the user's attention correspond to the highest tile watching percentages and thus contribute more to the overall perceived quality. Following up on these observations, it is logical to incorporate these values in representing the tiles' importance while assigning tile quality levels in bandwidth-constrained transmission.

Transmitting tiles at higher bitrates generally leads to an enhancement in perceived tile quality. However, this relationship is not particularly a straightforward one. Depending on the video content, increasing the bitrates of two different tiles may not yield the same degree of improvement in tile quality. Rather than focusing only on tiles bitrates, we also consider the contribution of each tile toward maximizing the perceived quality. Hence, our focus is on maximizing the WS-PSNR value, calculated over the user's FoV. 360° VQA metrics are specifically designed to estimate the quality of omnidirectional videos. Therefore, the choice of optimizing the viewport's WS-PSNR directly leads to improving the end user's viewing experience. Furthermore, it is important to note that our method described below does not impose any restriction on viewport tiles having the same quality level.

Figure 1: User's viewport within a 360° video, where the ERP projected video is divided into an 8x8 tile grid.

Figure 2: Tiles watching percentage (%), averaged over a one-second segment.

In our system model, the VR user receives the tiles of a 360° video and uses a HMD to view the omnidirectional content, as illustrated in Figure 3. As videos are usually split into short temporal segments upon streaming, we deal with each video segment as an independent video that consists of K temporal frames. The 360° video is provided in the ERP format. It has pixel dimensions of $P_H \times P_V$ and is divided into $M \times N$ tiles that belong to the set of tiles $T = \{T_{1,1}, \dots, T_{m,n}, \dots, T_{M,N}\}$. Therefore, each tile, $T_{m,n}$, consists of $(P_H/M) \times (P_V/N)$ pixels. The user's FoV is of size $F_H \times F_V$ and at any time k , the user's viewing direction is given as pitch and yaw angles that decide the displayed content.

Figure 3: VR user receiving multi-quality 360° video tiles.

Depending on the tiling arrangement, user's viewing direction, and FoV size, the user watches a subset of the overall tiles that comprise frame k , such that $T_k \in T$. Some of the tiles in T_k , however, do not entirely fall within the user's FoV. We denote the tiles viewing percentage as $a_{k,m,n}$ to quantify the proportion of pixels in tile $T_{m,n}$ that are within the user's FoV at time k . The averaging of $a_{k,m,n}$ over K frames is represented by $a_{m,n}$ and is calculated as follows

$$a_{m,n} = \frac{M \cdot N}{K \cdot P_H \cdot P_V} \cdot \sum_{k=1}^K \sum_{i=1}^{P_H/M} \sum_{j=1}^{P_V/N} \Psi_{k,m,n}(i,j) \quad (1)$$

In (1), $\Psi_{k,m,n}(i,j)$ equals 1 when pixel ij in tile $T_{m,n}$ is being watched by the user at time k , and 0 otherwise.

Each tile, $T_{m,n}$, is available on the server at a number of Q qualities. The tile representation, $T_{m,n,q}$, corresponds to tile $T_{m,n}$ at quality level q and has bitrate denoted $b_{m,n,q}$. Higher q values correspond to higher quality levels with higher bitrates. The goal of our tile selection framework is to deliver the highest perceived quality to the user within the constraints of the total available bandwidth BW .

We chose the viewport WS-PSNR (VWS-PSNR) as the quality metric to represent the user's perceived quality and use it as the assessment metric in this work. The VWS-PSNR metric is calculated in dB using equations (2)-(4).

$$VWS_PSNR = \frac{1}{K} \sum_{k=1}^K 10 \cdot \log_{10} \frac{MAX_I^2}{VWMSE_k} \quad (2)$$

$$VWMSE_k = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^{P_H} \sum_{j=1}^{P_V} \Psi_k(i,j) \cdot (y(i,j) - y'(i,j))^2 \cdot w(i,j)}{\sum_{i=1}^{P_H} \sum_{j=1}^{P_V} \Psi_k(i,j) \cdot w(i,j)} \quad (3)$$

$$w(i,j) = \cos \left(\frac{j + 0.5 - \frac{P_H}{2}}{P_H} \right) \pi \quad (4)$$

We define $\Psi_k(i,j)$, used in equation (3), in a similar manner to $\Psi_{k,m,n}(i,j)$, with the exception that the pixel position is in respect to the whole frame. MAX_I used in equation (2) denotes the maximum possible intensity level of the video frame, which typically has the value of 255.

Instead of calculating the viewport quality from pixel difference values each time, we propose working with the quality metric values at the tile level. This avoids the delay required at the pixel-level calculations and provides an adequate approximation for the actual values. We, therefore, define the quantity $G_{m,n}$ to quantify the contribution level of tile $T_{m,n}$ to the overall viewport quality.

$$G_{m,n} = a_{m,n} \cdot WS_PSNR_{m,n} \quad (5)$$

Where $WS_PSNR_{m,n}$ is calculated in a similar manner to (2), but with only including the pixels within tile $T_{m,n}$.

We formulate a tile quality selection optimization problem to maximize the value:

$$\max_x \sum_{m=1}^M \sum_{n=1}^N \sum_{q=1}^Q G_{m,n,q} x_{m,n,q} \quad (6)$$

s.t.

$$\sum_{m=1}^M \sum_{n=1}^N \sum_{q=1}^Q b_{m,n,q} x_{m,n,q} \leq BW$$

$$\sum_{q=1}^Q x_{m,n,q} = 1, \quad x_{m,n,q} \in \{0,1\}$$

The resulting problem is a multi-choice knapsack problem (MCKP). The MCKP is known to be an NP-hard problem. Therefore, to perform the tile selection in a fast manner, we implement a greedy algorithm to tackle the problem of maximizing the value in equation (6) as described in the next section.

A. Tested Algorithms

To tackle the problem introduced in Section 3, we apply a greedy algorithm to solve it, and assess its performance based on the constructed viewport's quality, i.e., the VWS-PSNR metric defined in equation (2). We test our proposed method in comparison with two other approaches which are all described as follows:

- MCKP-Greedy (proposed): The deployed greedy algorithm prioritizes tiles with higher potential gains, represented by the increase of the $G_{m,n}$ value over the increase in tile bitrate $b_{m,n}$ and assigns higher quality levels to them.
- MCKP-Greedy_2: The MCKP-Greedy_2 simulated method is similar to our solution, but without accounting for the viewed portion of each tile. Thus the value $a_{m,n}$ is set to 1 for all tiles in the user's viewport.
- Same_Q: This approach assigns the same quality level to all tiles within the user's viewport. It selects the maximum possible quality level that would result in a total bitrate that is lower than the available bandwidth.

Table 1: Dataset Summary.

Video Title	Average Tile Bitrate (Mbps)			
	QP=37	QP=32	QP=27	QP=22
PressConference	0.043	0.075	0.152	0.369
Shooting	0.048	0.097	0.262	0.909
Pagoda	0.042	0.083	0.216	0.725
Salon	0.097	0.203	0.467	1.192
ConcertLive	0.067	0.139	0.340	0.847
DrivingInCity	0.028	0.057	0.154	0.481
FootballMatch	0.080	0.162	0.370	1.034
GreatWall	0.050	0.088	0.187	0.446
BoatInPark	0.058	0.128	0.356	0.989
BuddhaCave	0.044	0.094	0.259	0.844
DrivingInCountry	0.066	0.131	0.298	0.732
XiaoGuang	0.059	0.106	0.250	0.705

B. Dataset

We carried out our evaluation based on the ODV-VQA dataset [8]. We selected the twelve 4K 360° videos which are provided in raw format. Each of these videos is ten seconds long and has a framerate of 30fps. We use FFMPEG [9] to cut the videos into one-second segments and deal with each segment as a separate video. We also use FFMPEG to divide each segment into an 8x8 tile grid. We encode each of the resulting tiles independently at four different levels (QP=22,27,32,37). Table 1 lists the selected videos along with the resulting average tile bitrate at each encoding level. The ODV-VQA dataset also provides head movement (HM) traces, collected from users watching the videos using HMDs, which we utilize in our evaluation.

C. Performance Evaluation

We test the tile quality selection algorithms described in section 4.1 under bandwidth values in the range of 2-18 Mbps. We compare our proposed greedy solution (MCKP-Greedy) with MCKP-Greedy_2 and Same_Q. To assess the performance of the implemented methods, we calculate the VWS-PSNR as defined in equations (2)-(4) and average it over all video segments and the viewing data of 20 different

users. Figure 4 illustrates the performance of our tile quality selection method, in comparison with MCKP-Greedy_2 and Same_Q. The figure shows the delivered viewport qualities, in terms of VWS-PSNR, as received by the users. Our proposed algorithm outperforms the other two methods in terms of VWS-PSNR. This is due to prioritizing tiles with high viewing percentages over edge tiles which are only partially watched.

Figure 4: Viewport WS-PSNR values with respect to the available bandwidth.

Figure 5: Example of the tile selection by the proposed method. Darker shades are given to higher quality levels.

To illustrate how our proposed method prioritizes important tiles, we provide an example of the tiles' qualities chosen by the MCKP-Greedy in Figure 5. The figure shows the selected quality levels for the same video segment and viewport data under four different values of BW. When the available bandwidth is low, all tiles are assigned the lowest available quality level. The remaining bandwidth is utilized to increase the quality of center tiles that have the highest effect on the overall quality. At higher bandwidth values, edge tiles start to compete on the resources, as center tiles would be already covered at high qualities.

V. CONCLUSION

We introduced the problem of tile quality assignment that maximizes the user's viewport quality in bandwidth-constrained 360° video streaming and formalized it as a MCKP. We proposed to solve this problem using a greedy algorithm and conducted an empirical evaluation to assess its performance using a 360° video viewing dataset. Our method prioritizes tiles with a higher impact on the delivered viewport's WS-PSNR by incorporating the tiles' viewing ratios in the decision-making. The simulation results confirmed the benefits of enhancing the viewport quality through the prioritization of fully-watched tiles.

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